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Updated EU Demand Side Radar

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D5.5 – Updated EU Demand Side Radar

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
EUCloudEdgeIoT	Short Name to refer to The European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum, an inter-project umbrella initiative of which UNLOCK CEI is a member
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
VCA	Value Chain Adopter
WP	Work Package

Keywords

Cloud-Edge-IoT; Computing; Continuum; Demand-Supply Dialogue; Communication; Engagement, Demand Side Radar

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the progress of the Unlock-CEI EU Demand Side Radar and the activity of its designing and implementation after the release of the first version in M18. The first version of radar was released in M18 in which the infographics based on the results of the demand landscape analysis were demonstrated (WP1). Starting M19, the design finalization, data collection and implementation of the updated version of demand side radar took place. The current online radar visualises CEI use cases based on CEI technologies, vertical sectors, the addressable market and some technical requirements. It includes more than 70 CEI use-cases based on an extensive data collection performed during Unlock-CEI project (WP2). Following the introduction the document describes the steps taken to specify the design, collect the information and develop the EU Demand Side Radar. The core part of the document shows the logic and methodology behind the demand side radar and its visualisation available on EU Cloud Edge IoT website¹. In the last chapter of the document, we describe how the radar can be used by different stakeholders from research and industry including also RIAs and other EU projects.

¹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/cei-demand-radar/>

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1. Introduction

The EU Demand Side Radar is the outcome of Task 5.2 within the Work Package 5 on Communication and Dissemination. The task has been led by IDC ITALIA (IDC) and its goal has been to design and develop an interactive and automated online overview on the Cloud-Edge-IoT demand landscape. The type of this deliverable is “OTHER” since the major output of the task is a tool which is available on EU-CEI portal. The current document provides a summary of the progress and final results of this task and it’s the updated version of the first summary report of demand side radar in D5.4 submitted in M18.

1.1 Purpose of this document

The purpose of the EU Demand Side Radar of UNLOCK-CEI is to provide an illustrative overview about the main trends and insights of Cloud-Edge-IoT market both at the general level and use-case level. The radar leverages the outputs generated within CEI demand oriented work packages of UNLOCK-CEI in particular WP1 CEI Demand Landscape and WP2 Market Scenarios and Guidance.

In this document, we describe the methodology, design, data collection and implementation of the demand side radar. The online radar visualises CEI use cases across five verticals and their specific characteristics relevant for market adoption such as data collection volume, data collection frequency, data collection bandwidth and annual market after roll-out. The use cases are collected from the industrial field research done within the project through WP1 and WP2. Both WPs provided extensive market analysis in terms of categories of market spotlight use-cases for CEI and the detailed sub use-cases under each category.

1.2 Link to other deliverables

This document is connected to the following project deliverables:

- **D.1.1 & D1.2** Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape analysis reports: outcomes of the market landscape, survey efforts and industrial use cases presented in these deliverables were fundamental to feed the content of the radar. These deliverables have been also the main information collection for the first version of radar and the other preliminary visualisation tools developed as part of T5.2 and detailed in D5.2.
- **D.2.1** Readiness framework and service requirements: the preliminary mapping of CEI use-cases and their service characteristics were defined in this report and the information were used for the first visualization phase of the use-cases in radar.
- **D2.2** Preliminary market scenarios and pathways to the future open European CEI ecosystem: The deliverable provides a detailed mapping of more than 70 CEI use-cases across five sector (an updated version of the ones presented in D2.1) and the updated list was used to update the demand side radar information and add the new use-case.
- **D5.1** Communications, dissemination and engagement plan and subsequent iterations (**D5.2** and **D5.3**): The radar is an important element of the engagement strategy and fully supports its objectives
- **D5.4** EU Demand side radar (First version): D5.4 is the first version of demand side radar report and provided the progress of the activity from M1-M18 and the plan for the evolution of the radar by the end of the project.

1.3 Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows:

- **Design process and evolution of the demand side radar:** Following the introduction this chapter describes the steps taken to specify the design of the EU Demand Side Radar from the beginning of the project and its evolution within the project lifetime to achieve its final version.

- **Demand side radar tool overview:** This chapter provides the details about the approach and methodology to design the radar, how the information to feed the radar are collected, main dimensions of the radar, and how from a technical point of view the radar is implemented.
- **Exploitation of demand side radar:** This chapter describes how the demand side radar can be used by different stakeholders, the value it can provide and the plan to ensure its sustainability after the end of the project as an asset of EU-CEI.
- **Annex:** The Annex includes the visual version of the demand side radar on [Cloud-Edge-IoT Landscape - EUCloudEdgeIoT](#).

2. Design process and evolution of demand side radar

The activities to design and conceptualise the demand side radar started in M6 based on the first release of CEI demand landscape analysis in D1.1. As the project moved forward and other results and demand landscape analysis were generated, the concept and design of radar evolved and finalized to its current version. The phases are described below:

- **Initial ramp-up phase** (November 2022 – January 2023): regular meetings were scheduled and held between IDC (Task Leader) & Trust-IT (WP5 leader and task contributor) to initiate discussion on the possible features of the radar and the desired visualisation needs. Main highlights and decisions were shared with all the other partners during the second physical Consortium meeting in Prague (24th November 2022) and during the other online monthly meetings, when necessary.
- **Technical alignments:** After the first three months, at the end of **January 2023 (M08)**, a first technical meeting was organised with IT experts (partner COMMpla) to validate the implementation needs and the sources and platforms needed for the technical realisation of the tool.
- **First release of CEI demand dashboard:** At the end of **February 2023 (M09)**, a preliminary version of the demand landscape visualisation dashboards was produced. The aim was to represent the main market trends in an illustrative way. The trends were identified in WP1 and are complementary to the use case information that later were included in the radar tool.
- **Updated release of CEI demand dashboard:** In **June 2023**, the second main output were fed in the release of additional and updated dashboards (relying on D1.2 results) showcasing recent market trends. These dashboards are hosted on the same website section and are public.
- **Final conceptualization and design of demand side radar:** From **June 2023 to November 2023 the design concept of the demand side radar to visualize CEI use-cases was evolved through** several alignment calls between IDC and TRUST-IT and the CEI use-case mapping provided in WP2 by EGI. Eventually the design was finalized as explained in chapter 3.
- **Launch of radar and use-case visualization:** By **February 2024** the first version of demand side radar was implemented on EU-CEI portal representing CEI use-cases and their service characteristics for five main sectors.
- **Update of radar:** In **June 2024**, the radar was updated by feeding the updated version of CEI use-case mapping provided by WP2.

3. Demand side radar tool overview

Demand use-case radar² is a dynamic platform, produced by the UNLOCK-CEI CSA to illuminate the diverse landscape of CEI computing continuum. Through mapping more than 70 CEI use-cases across five sectors, it is a gateway to a comprehensive exploration of use-cases, with relevant characteristics such as Annual Market, and data collection volume. Through these characteristics it provides better understanding of potential impact and scalability of use-cases. Stakeholders can explore each use case's characteristics by clicking on the circles below. They can also filter use cases by selecting an industry or data collection (volume, bandwidth, frequency) of their choice.

3.1 Approach and lay-out

CEI Demand side radar is designed in a way to visualize the CEI use-cases and their most important service characteristics in a self-explanatory and user-friendly manner to make it easy for them to position different use-cases across the computing continuum and retrieve the information and service characteristics which are closest to their use-cases of their interest. Even though in D2.2, several service characteristics are mapped for each use-case it was not feasible to illustrate and visualize all those characteristics in the radar due to technical limits. Thus, a set of most relevant and strategic characteristics were selected to be visualized on the radar. The selected characteristics are described below:

- **Positionna in computing continuum:** The radar framework consists of 4 rings representing the distribution of workload across the computing continuum. Starting from the central ring representing the commercial cloud, the next rings represent the layers of continuum where the workload will be more closer to the edge of the device (From Cloud to Edge). Accordingly the rings are as the following from center to the outer space 1) commercial cloud 2) On-premise edge 3) Corporate data center 4) On-device edge. Positioning of each use-case in the rings is based on the work load distribution of the use-case across the computing continuum.
- **Sector :** Five sectors are visualized in the radar by color labeling. Each use-case color shows the sector of the use-case among the five sectors of agriculture, energy, healthcare, manufacturing and transportation.
- **Data collection volume:** Illustrated in the information box for each use-case, this characteristic shows the level of required data to be collected to implement the use-case from low to medium to high.
- **Data collection frequency:** Illustrated in the information box for each use-case, this characteristic shows how frequently the data needs to be collected to implement the use-case from low to medium to high.
- **Data collection bandwidth:** Illustrated in the information box for each use-case, this characteristic refers to the rate at which data can be gathered and transmitted across different layers of the computing continuum from low to medium to high.
- **Annual market after roll-out:** Illustrated in the information box for each use-case, it refers to the total potential revenue or market size that can be captured by the use-case once it has been fully deployed and established in the market over the course of a year.

Figures 1 and 2 show the implemented demand radar including the use-case and a screen shot of the radar with examples of use-cases information sheet.

² <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/cei-demand-radar/>

Figure 1. CEI demand side radar interface

Figure 2. Examples of use-cases visualization in the radar

3.2 Data collection for the tool

While for the first version of CEI demand dashboard the results of market analysis and Unlcock-CEI survey that were generated in WP1 (D1.1 and D1.2) were used, for the CEI demand side radar the results of CEI use-case mapping generated in WP2 were used as the main source of information (D 2.1 and D2.2). This evolution was based on the evolution of market analysis activities within the project in which in the first phase the main market trends and forecast were identified in the second phase a more details analysis at use-case level.

The use-case mapping was conducted by EGI based on the analysis of use-case selected by IDC in WP1 as the results of market analysis. The first version of the use-case mapping was generated based on an extensive desk research of market studies coding the use-cases based on the sector and categories. The details of the mapping and the methodology are described in D2.1 «Adoption readiness framework and service requirements»³. Figure 3 shows an example of use-cases coding for the agriculture sector.

#	Sector	Use Case (from IDC)	Use Case #	Use Case Solutions #	Use Case Solution
1	Agriculture	Remote Asset Monitoring and Tracking	A1	A1.1	Animals
2	Agriculture	Remote Asset Monitoring and Tracking	A1	A1.2	Crates
3	Agriculture	Precision Agriculture	A1	A1.3	Precision Crop Monitoring
4	Agriculture	Precision Agriculture	A2	A2.1	Irrigation System
5	Agriculture	Agricultural Equipment Automation	A2	A2.2	Robot Weeder
6	Agriculture	Agricultural Equipment Automation	A3	A3.1	Disease and parasite detection
7	Energy & Utilities	Smart Grid	E1	E1.1	Energy Monitoring and Demand Response in Real-Time
8	Energy & Utilities	Smart Grid	E1	E1.2	Renewable Energy Integration and Management
9	Energy & Utilities	Drone-Based Observation	E2	E2.1	Inspection and Maintenance of the Infrastructure
10	Energy & Utilities	Drone-Based Observation	E2	E2.2	Security and Asset Protection
11	Energy & Utilities	Employee Safety Monitoring	E3	E3.1	Monitoring of Equipment for Personal Protection
12	Energy & Utilities	Employee Safety Monitoring	E3	E3.2	Lone Worker Safety Monitoring
13	Healthcare	Hospital Asset Tracking	H1	H1.1a	Tracking Smart Assets (patient monitors)
14	Healthcare	Hospital Asset Tracking	H1	H1.1a	Tracking Dumb Assets (beds, wheelchairs)
15	Healthcare	Bedside Telemetry	H2	H2.1	In-hospital telemetry
16	Healthcare	AI-Enabled Diagnosis and Treatment Systems	H3	H3.1	Std. AI Models packaged for hospital use
17	Healthcare	Remote Patient Monitoring	H4	H4.1	In-home telemetry
18	Healthcare	Remote Patient Monitoring	H4	H4.2	Mobile telemetry
19	Healthcare	Remote Patient Monitoring	H4	H4.3	Ambulance telemetry
20	Manufacturing	Asset Monitoring and Maintenance	M1	M1.1	Condition Monitoring and Anomaly Detection
21	Manufacturing	Asset Monitoring and Maintenance	M1	M1.2	Energy Efficiency and Sustainability
22	Manufacturing	Autonomously Guided Vehicles (AGVs) and robots	M2	M2.1	Workforce Safety and Collaborative Robotic
23	Manufacturing	Autonomously Guided Vehicles (AGVs) and robots	M2	M2.2	Smart Fleet Management
24	Manufacturing	Visual Inspections and Quality Control	M3	M3.1	Production Line Monitoring in Real Time
25	Manufacturing	Visual Inspections and Quality Control	M3	M3.2	Inspections via Remote Vision
26	Transportation	Port and Warehouse Automation	T1	T1.1	Container Tracking and Management
27	Transportation	Port and Warehouse Automation	T1	T1.2	Automated Inventory Management
28	Transportation	Fleet Tracking and Freight Monitoring	T2	T2.1	Trucks
29	Transportation	Fleet Tracking and Freight Monitoring	T2	T2.2	Railroad cars
30	Transportation	Fleet Tracking and Freight Monitoring	T2	T2.3	Containers
31	Transportation	Fleet Tracking and Freight Monitoring	T2	T2.4	Ships
32	Transportation	Autonomous Vehicles and Infrastructure	T3	T3.1	Advanced Traffic Management
33	Transportation	Fleet Tracking and Freight Monitoring	T3	T3.2	Smart Charging Infrastructure for Electric Vehicles

Figure 3 Example of use-case coding for agriculture sector (Source: Unlock-CEI D2.1)

The coded use-cases then were used to define the service characteristics as described in D2.1. An example of some service characteristics of agriculture use-case are illustrated in Figure 4.

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8283428>

Source Use Case (from IDC)	Remote Asset Monitoring and Tracking	Remote Asset Monitoring and Tracking	Precision Agriculture	Precision Agriculture	Agricultural Equipment Automation	Agricultural Equipment Automation
Use Case #	A1	A1	A2	A2	A3	A3
Use Case Solution	Animals	Crates	Precision Crop Monitoring	Irrigation System	Robot weeder	Disease and parasite detection
Use Case Solution #	A1.1	A1.2	A2.1	A2.2	A3.1	A3.2
Low Latency	N	N	Y	N	Y	N
Low-cost Local Data	Y	Y	Partial	Y	Y	Y
Services & Roles						
Design	Animal specific, define suitable IoT devices (GPS, RFID tag, microchips) and consider habitat and behaviour.	Manufacture. Hi durability needed keeping into consideration different weather conditions, and elements (sunlight exposure, temperature variations, cold-warm, rainfall, erosion)	System integrators for the software and manufacturers for the hardware	IoT sensor placing, data collection and integration with forecast services.	System integrators for the software and manufacturers for the hardware	Domain experts, engineers. Specific diseases or parasites, environmental factors, and crop characteristics. The design will be needed in the long term to keep updated with new threats and changing conditions.
Install	Physical installation on the animals. Training to animal handles for device management.	Crates producer	No installation needed for satellites/drones. Monitoring devices are placed in the fields.	Integration with current irrigation systems, professional may require for wiring and calibration.	No physical installation needed for robots. Configuration needed.	Ensuring proper functioning of sensors and connectivity.
Operate	Farmers take care of day-to-day operation + detecting anomalies and respond to alerts.	Mainly automated + operators-scanners to inspect	Data can be elaborated on site through Edge systems with some alarm planned. Data from drones and satellites need to be elaborated on cloud. All together they are elaborated on cloud.	No/low maintenance required.	Robots have integrated edge capabilities to manage the weeding process. Robots send information to a remote system to have a double check and history to elaborate predictive management of the fields.	Agronomists, researchers. Monitoring
Value-Add	Analyse animal behaviour provided new	Asset mapping, status tracking, utilisation	This integrated system can help in managing agricultural production	Optimizing irrigation schedules, water usage and	Simplify the weeding process and manage it in a pre-emptive	Identify disease and parasite patterns.

Figure 4 Example of use-case characteristics for agriculture sector (Source: Unlock-CEI D2.1)

In a later phase, the use-case mapping was evolved by defining the detailed characteristics for each use-case such as data collection volume, data collection frequency, data collection bandwidth, total addressable market, total annual market after roll-out, etc. The final use-case list with the detailed characteristics (which has been the base of D.2.)⁴ was used as the main data input for the radar. Figures 5 and 6 show examples of mapping use-cases based on data collection volume and frequency.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/12732567>

Level	Use Case (from IDC D1.2 Section 4)	High	Medium	Low
L1: Location tracking	Agriculture Animal Tagging	0%	100%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Asset location tracking	33%	67%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Employee safety monitoring	100%	0%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Fleet tracking	50%	50%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Hospital Asset Tracking	0%	100%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Passenger traffic flow	100%	0%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Total	54%	46%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Drone-based observation	100%	0%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Quality of shipment conditions	0%	100%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Vehicle and infrastructure inspection	100%	0%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Video security and surveillance	80%	0%	20%
L2: Visual inspection	Visual inspection - quality/integrity	0%	0%	100%
L2: Visual inspection	Total	67%	11%	22%
L3: Condition monitoring	Agriculture Field Monitoring	0%	0%	100%
L3: Condition monitoring	Bedside Telemetry	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	75%	25%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Field service technician monitoring	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Food traceability	0%	0%	100%
L3: Condition monitoring	Livestock monitoring	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Regulatory compliance	25%	50%	25%
L3: Condition monitoring	Remote Health Monitoring	0%	100%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Remote network management	0%	100%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Visual Inspection	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Total	52%	33%	14%
L4: Predictive maintenance	AI-enabled Diagnosis and Treatment	0%	0%	100%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring and maintenance	0%	0%	100%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring and maintenance - OEM	0%	0%	100%

Figure 5 Data collection frequency for mapped use-cases (Source: Unlock-CEI D2.2)

Level	Use Case (from IDC D1.2 Section 4)	High	Medium	Low
L1: Location tracking	Agriculture Animal Tagging	0%	0%	100%
L1: Location tracking	Asset location tracking	0%	33%	67%
L1: Location tracking	Employee safety monitoring	0%	0%	100%
L1: Location tracking	Fleet tracking	0%	50%	50%
L1: Location tracking	Hospital Asset Tracking	0%	0%	100%
L1: Location tracking	Passenger traffic flow	100%	0%	0%
L1: Location tracking	Total	8%	15%	77%
L2: Visual inspection	Drone-based observation	0%	100%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Quality of shipment conditions	100%	0%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Vehicle and infrastructure inspection	100%	0%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Video security and surveillance	100%	0%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Visual inspection - quality/integrity	100%	0%	0%
L2: Visual inspection	Total	89%	11%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Agriculture Field Monitoring	0%	0%	100%
L3: Condition monitoring	Bedside Telemetry	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Employee safety monitoring	0%	87%	13%
L3: Condition monitoring	Field service technician monitoring	0%	100%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Food traceability	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Livestock monitoring	0%	100%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Regulatory compliance	0%	50%	50%
L3: Condition monitoring	Remote Health Monitoring	0%	100%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Remote network management	0%	100%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Visual inspection - quality/integrity	100%	0%	0%
L3: Condition monitoring	Total	14%	67%	19%
L4: Predictive maintenance	AI-enabled Diagnosis and Treatment	100%	0%	0%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring and maintenance	67%	33%	0%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring and maintenance - OEM	100%	0%	0%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Asset monitoring and maintenance - retrofit	100%	0%	0%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Robots or augmented-reality-assisted surgery	100%	0%	0%
L4: Predictive maintenance	Sensor-based diagnostics & maintenance	0%	100%	0%

Figure 6 Data collection volume for mapped use-cases (Source: Unlock-CEI D2.2)

3.3 Implementation of the demand side radar

The development of the Demand Side Radar tool was a collaborative effort among the partners COMMpla, IDC and EGI aimed at providing a comprehensive and user-friendly interface to visualise the selected demand-side use cases in the Cloud, Edge, and IoT domains. The implementation process included two main steps, namely 1) the conceptual design and 2) the actual deployment of the tool. The initial phase consisted in creating a graphical mockup of the tool, essential to define the filters, data points and overall information that would be visualised within the tool. The design was produced by COMMpla, based on the information contained in an Excel database prepared by EGI. Following the approval of the mockup, in the second phase, the COMMpla team undertook the technical implementation of the Demand Side Radar.

The tool was developed using open-source software, which was integrated with custom code to meet the specific needs of the project. The choice of open-source software allowed for greater flexibility in adapting the tool, enabling the implementation of advanced features such as dynamic interaction and the management of large data volumes. The code was primarily written in PHP and JavaScript, leveraging the WordPress platform as a foundation due to its versatility and the wide range of plugins available. Additionally, modifications were made to the core software to enhance performance and optimise the tool's usability in the context of continuous data growth.

The first version of the Demand Side Radar was completed by January 2024 and was presented at the project review. This version provided an initial set of use cases and allowed users to filter and explore these cases. Based on some feedback received by the platform users and with the number of collected use cases growing, a second iteration was later produced in May 2024. This iteration included additional details on the use cases and expanded the number of cases displayed, providing a more comprehensive overview of the demand side landscape.

4. Exploitation of demand side radar

Demand side radar is a tool available to all stakeholders to gain a better understanding of the existing CEI use-cases and their technical and market characteristics across five sectors. It helps end-users to gain insights about the already existing CEI use-cases in the market, their market potential in future and thus position their potential use-cases of interest. On the other hand, it provides the suppliers an overview of the direction of the market evolution in terms of CEI applications and the specific requirements that users are interested in.

The current version of the demand side radar will be available on the EUcloudEdgeIoT platform event after the end of Unlock-CEI project in November 2024. Moreover, through the new funded CSA, CEI-Sphere, which will start in October 2024; the radar will maintain its sustainability phase by encompassing further developments and evolution under the scope of Large Scale Pilots that will be supported by CEI-Sphere. The detailed sustainability plan of the radar will be provided in D5.9 (Updated sustainability plan) in M30 (November 2024).